

O'ZBEKISTONNING YEUII MAMLAKATLARI BILAN IQTISODIY HAMKORLIGI: HOZIRGI HOLATI VA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot O'zbekiston Respublikasi va Evroosiyo iqtisodiy ittifoqi mamlakatlari o'rtasidagi hamkorlikning hozirgi holati va istiqbollari bag'ishlangan.

O'zbekistonning asosiy savdo sheriklari va Evropa Ittifoqi doirasidagi O'zbekistonning istiqbollari tahlil qilindi. Xulosada tadqiqotning asosiy ilmiy natijalari umumlashtiriladi, tarkibidan kelib chiqadigan ilmiy xulosalar shakllantiriladi va O'zbekistonda qulay iqtisodiy muhitni shakllantirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar ishlab chiqiladi.

Annotation. This article is devoted to the current state and prospects of cooperation between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the countries of the Eurasian Economic Union. The main trade partners of Uzbekistan and the prospects of Uzbekistan within the EAEU are analyzed. In the conclusion, the main scientific results of the study are summarized, scientific conclusions arising from the content are formulated, and recommendations for the formation of a favorable economic environment in Uzbekistan are developed

Kalit so'zlar: tashqi savdo, Yevroosiyo iqtisodiy ittifoqi, O'zbekiston, eksport va import, tariflar.

Key words: foreign trade, Eurasian Economic Union, Uzbekistan, export and import, tariffs

Economic integration is the process of economic interaction between countries, leading to the convergence of economic mechanisms, taking the form of interstate agreements and coordinately regulated by interstate bodies. Integration processes lead to the development of economic regionalism, as a result of which individual groups of countries create among themselves more favorable conditions for trade, and in some cases for the interregional movement of factors of production than for other countries. Despite its obvious protectionist traits, economic regionalism is not considered a negative factor as long as it does not worsen the conditions for trade with the rest of the world.

The prerequisites for economic integration are the comparability of the levels of market development of the participating countries, their geographical proximity,

the commonality of the problems they face, the desire to accelerate market reforms and not stay away from the ongoing integration processes.

On March 29, 1996, an agreement was signed between Belarus, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Russia on deepening integration processes in economic and humanitarian areas. On the basis of this agreement, a new organization was created between the CIS states - the Customs Union (CU). The supreme body of the Customs Union was the interstate fee, which includes the heads of state and ministers of foreign affairs.

In 1999, Tajikistan also became a member of the Customs Union. In 2000, five states (Russia, Kazakhstan, Belarus, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan) agreed to transform the CU into the Eurasian Economic Community, resulting in the formation of the Eurasian Economic Community, which has an international status.

Currently the Eurasian Economic Union is organized as an international economic association that includes five countries: Russia, Kazakhstan, Belarus, Armenia and Kyrgyzstan.

The main goal of creating the EAEU was to update the national economies of all partner countries and increase competitiveness at a new level. Eurasian integration in the customs sphere means trade without duties and customs borders in order to help partners increase trade, reduce prices for goods and products imported from the member countries of the association, including by creating equal competitive conditions for manufacturers.

It is worth noting that the key principle of the EAEU is the creation of favorable economic and trade conditions for the foreign economic activity of the countries that have joined this union.

Thus, the key issue in analyzing the activities of the EAEU is its features of customs regulation, both between the participating countries and between the participating countries and other states. At the same time, the development prospects and its main directions of the EAEU include not only the improvement of customs regulation, but also the joint process of stimulating integration processes in the financial sector, in the development of innovative technologies and the production of industrial products.

By joining the EAEU, Uzbekistan will become a member of the customs area, where the Unified Customs Tariff (ETT) is applied by all the members. The adoption of the EAEU unified customs tariff system means the unification of the rates of import customs duties of Uzbekistan and the EAEU in relation to third countries, and they will be regulated by the EAEU Unified Customs Tariff. Since at present, the system of customs tariffs in Uzbekistan differs significantly from

the similar system of the EAEU, their unification presupposes a significant adjustment of the rates of import customs duties in Uzbekistan.

The analysis of the impact of membership of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the EAEU on the macroeconomic indicators of the state has been conducted by N.Sirajiddinov, G.Sultanova, N.Kurbanbaeva and L.Mingishev. The researchers implemented the model of TRIST for the reasons of measuring the effect of Eurasian economic integration of the Republic of Uzbekistan on such indicators as the import volume, import directions and revenues of the budget from the import taxes.

According to the estimates of Sirajiddinov, Sultanova, Kurbanbaeva and Mingishev, the average import tariff rate in Uzbekistan is currently 9.5%. Due to the existing differences in the structures of economies, there are significant differences between the rates of import duties of certain commodity groups and items in Uzbekistan and in the EAEU: for some sections and commodity items of the Commodity Nomenclature of Foreign Economic Activity, the average rates of import duties in Uzbekistan are significantly higher than in the EAEU, then for others - below.

An important consequence of the entry and unification of the rates of import customs duties of Uzbekistan with the EAEU will be a change in the revenues to the state budget from customs duties.

An increase in import duty rates in relation to goods from countries that are not members of the EAEU and the CIS will lead to an increase in state budget revenues, provided that the demand for imported goods as a result of an increase in import tariff rates and the domestic price level decreases to a lesser extent than an increase in imports. tariff (low price elasticity of demand).

Conversely, if the demand for imported goods is highly elastic, then an increase in import tariff rates and domestic prices will lead to an even greater reduction in demand for these imported goods, then state budget revenues will decrease as a result of an increase in import tariff rates.

Calculations show that Uzbekistan's accession to the EAEU will lead to a decrease in revenues to the state budget from import customs duties in general by

1 269 667 thousand USD, or by 53.9% in relation to the amount of revenues to the state budget before joining the EAEU. At the same time, the total amount of losses of the state budget from customs payments (including VAT and excise tax on imports) will decrease by 1 367 977 thousand USD, or by 16.2% compared to the income of the state budget from customs payments before the country's accession to the EAEU.

Today the Republic of Uzbekistan is going through a critical stage in its historical development. For the first time in the past 30 years, the political system is seriously changing, foreign policy priorities are clearly defined, new in essence foreign economic relations are being built, based on pragmatism and the most flexible use of modern realities in the national interests of the Republic. The country has developed a specific strategy for ensuring economic security, taking into account its own national priorities, actively diversifying its foreign economic relations.

Below is a table showing the directions of export from the Republic of Uzbekistan:

Table 1. Core partners for export of the Republic of Uzbekistan (from 2016 to 2020 in thousands of USD)

This means that the key partners of Uzbekistan in terms of the export directions are such states as China, Russian Federation, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Afghanistan and Kyrgyzstan.

China for the last years accounted for 12-20% of the total exports of Uzbekistan. The Russian Federation had about 10-15% of Uzbek exports. There has been a decrease of a share of exports to the Republic of Kazakhstan. Turkey accounts for about 5-7% of exports of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Afghanistan accounts for about 5% of Uzbek exports. There was a huge increase of the share of the Republic of Kyrgyzstan in terms of exports of the Republic of Uzbekistan – the indicator increases from 1% to 5% over the last 5 years.

Figure 1. Export volumes of the Republic of Uzbekistan (from 2016 to 2020 in thousands of USD)

For the last 5 years, the volume of exports from the Republic of Uzbekistan has been increasing. Even though the exports volume faced a decrease in 2020, the previous years were showing an increase of about 5-12% per year.

Figure 2. Export directions of the Republic of Uzbekistan (from 2016 to 2020 in thousands of USD)

As to the directions of exports from the Republic of Uzbekistan, it should be noted that exports volume to the Republic of Kyrgyzstan and Turkey is increasing over the last years. There was a negative trend in exports volume to such states as China and the Russian Federation over the last 5 years.

Below is a table showing the directions of import from the Republic of Uzbekistan:

Table 3. Core partners for import of the Republic of Uzbekistan (from 2016 to 2020 in thousands of USD)

This means that the key partners of Uzbekistan in terms of the import to the state are such states as China, the Russian Federation, the Republic of Korea, the Republic of Kazakhstan, Turkey and Germany.

China for the last years accounted for about 20% of the total imports to Uzbekistan. The Russian Federation had about also about 20% in terms of the imports to the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Republic of Korea accounted for 7-10% and the Republic of Kazakhstan for 7-9% of the total imports of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The share of Turkey and Germany over the last 5 years has been in the interval of 4-5%.

Figure 3. Import volumes of the Republic of Uzbekistan (from 2016 to 2020 in thousands of USD)

For the last 5 years, the volume of imports to the Republic of Uzbekistan has been also increasing. It was a decrease in 2020, however the previous years were showing a positive trend of about 10-20% per year.

Figure 4. Import directions of the Republic of Uzbekistan (from 2016 to 2020 in thousands of USD)

As to the major exporters to the Republic of Uzbekistan, all core exporters to the Republic of Uzbekistan could export more to the state in 2020 rather than in 2016. Almost all of the given states could double their exports to the Republic of Uzbekistan within the given period of time.

The following table and the figure indicate data about the structure of foreign trade of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

Uzbekistan received observer status in the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU). The corresponding decision was made on 11th December, 2020 at a meeting of the Supreme Eurasian Economic Council.

“We attach great importance to the development of close and multifaceted cooperation with the EAEU. It is important to use the potential of our countries, jointly remove barriers and obstacles in trade relations, mutually form new markets” said the President Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the meeting.

Uzbekistan actively uses the observer status with the Eurasian Economic Union. In the spring, the Republic adopted a roadmap for the development of cooperation with the EAEU, which, among other things, includes the harmonization of legislation with the norms of the union. By the end of the year, a representative office of the Eurasian Development Bank may open in Uzbekistan. And full-fledged integration into the EAEU, according to Russian Prime Minister Mikhail Mishustin, will provide additional opportunities for the growth of the Uzbek economy and tangible advantages for citizens.

The following table presents the export volumes from Uzbekistan as to the states of the EAEU with the rate in the total export of the state:

Table 5. Exports of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the EAEU states (for the period of 2020)

As Table 5 shows, the EAEU states account for 21.2% of exports from the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020. The following figure shows the shares of exports volumes from the Republic of Uzbekistan within the EAEU states:

Figure 6. Shares of exports of the Republic of Uzbekistan within the EAEU states (for the period of 2020)

Figure 6 shows that the core importer of Uzbek products within the EAEU is the Russian Federation – it accounts for just a half of exports from the Republic of Uzbekistan within the EAEU states. The Republic of Kazakhstan and the Republic of Kyrgyzstan have both of about a quarter. This means that the shares of the Republic of Belarus and Armenia in exports of the Republic of Uzbekistan within the EAEU states is quite low.

The following table presents the export volumes from Uzbekistan as to the states of the EAEU with the rate in the total export of the state:

Table 6. Imports of the Republic of Uzbekistan from the EAEU states (for the period of 2020)

As Table 6 shows, the EAEU states account for 31.46% of imports to the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020. The following figure shows the shares of imports volumes to the Republic of Uzbekistan from the EAEU states:

Figure 7. Shares of imports to the Republic of Uzbekistan from the EAEU states (for the period of 2020)

Figure 7 shows that the core exporter to Uzbekistan within the EAEU is also the Russian Federation – it accounts for 63% of imports among the EAEU states. The Republic of Kazakhstan has the share of 32% among the EAUE states. Republic of Belarus, Armenia and the Republic of Kyrgyzstan have quite low shares among the states of the EAEU in terms of exports to the Republic of Uzbekistan .

The processes of economic integration in the Eurasian area have almost the same possible positive and negative factors for the economies considering whether to apply an accession to the Eurasian Economic Union. For the Republic of Uzbekistan, it was also important to consider the possible advantages and drawbacks from its membership in the EAEU.

At the current moment of time, the Republic of Uzbekistan is an observer in the Eurasian Economic Union. By considering the policies of the Union and the experience of the states-members, it was possible to find out the following

possible advantages for the Republic of Uzbekistan from its membership in the EAEU:

1. A possible increase of exports to the members of the EAEU;
2. Formation of common labor market which will provide labor migrants from Uzbekistan with an opportunity of simplified migration procedures within the states of the EAEU;
3. An increase of direct investments from the states of the EAEU;
4. Liberalization of trade regime of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Educational portal «Economics and Management» - <http://ecsocman.hse.ru/text/19280377/>
2. State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics
3. Боброва В.В. Новый таможенный кодекс ЕАЭС как эффективный инструмент государственного регулирования внешней торговли // Региональная экономика и управление. – 2017. - № 1 (49)
4. Зиядуллаев У. Международные внешнеэкономические связи Республики Узбекистан и перспективы их развития // Iqtisodiyot va innovatsion texnologiyalar. 2020. №45, стр. 245-255
5. Сивенкова А. И., Шуклина З. Н. Особенности таможенного оформления в условиях функционирования Евразийского Экономического Союза // Молодой ученый. – 2017. – №6. – С. 297-300
6. Сиражиддинов Н., Султанова Г., Курбанбаева, Н., Мингишев Л. Социально-экономическое развитие Республики Узбекистан и Евразийское партнерство: стратегия и анализ тенденций // Университет мировой экономики и дипломатии, 2020
7. Хасанов У. Узбекистан и ЕАЭС: интеграция выгоднее «опоры на собственные силы» <https://uwed.uz/ru/news/fulltext/1681>